

**1ST CONGRESS OF THE MONTENEGRIN
ASSOCIATION OF HEMATOLOGISTS**

WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION

12. - 15.09, 2024.
BECICI (BUDVA), MONTENEGRO

MAH 2024

**KNJIGA SAŽETAKA
ABSTRACT BOOK**

Pozdravna riječ

Poštovane kolegice i kolege,

Dragi prijatelji,

U ime Udruženja hematologa Crne Gore, velika mi je čast i zadovoljstvo poželjeti Vam dobrodošlicu na 1. Kongres Udruženja hematologa Crne Gore sa međunarodnim učešćem (MAH 2024), koji se održava u Budvi, od 12.- 15. septembra 2024. godine.

Pored velikog broja priznatih stručnjaka iz oblasti hematologije, kongresu će prisustvovati i kolege iz dijagnostike (patohistološke, imunohistohemijske, molekularne genetike, protočne citometrije), koje su od neprocjenjivog značaja za adekvatan pristup našim pacijentima. Učešće su uzeli eminentni stručnjaci iz velikog broja država: Velike Britanije, Španije, Grčke, Njemačke, Turske, Albanije, Rumunije, Holandije, Srbije, Slovenije, Hrvatske, Bosne i Hercegovine, Sjeverne Makedonije. Od strane Ljekarske komore Crne Gore kongres je akreditovan kao međunarodni.

Teme su veoma aktuelne, update-ovane, te govore o aktuelnostima kako dijagnostike, tako i liječenja malignih hematoloških bolesti, uz teme iz domena benigne hematologije i hemostaze. Govoriće se takođe o transplantaciji matičnim ćelijama hematopoeze, kao i savremenom tretmanu CAR T ćelijama.

Lord Bajron je pisao o Crnoj Gori: „U trenutku postanka planete, najljepši susret kopna i mora desio se sigurno na crnogorskoj obali“. Nadamo se da će Vaš susret sa Crnom Gorom biti jednako lijep, da će njenom autentičnošću stvoriti ambijent za unapređenje profesionalnih i prijateljskih veza.

Srdačno,

Dr Enisa Žarić

Predsjednik udruženja hematologa Crne Gore

Predsjednik Kongresa

Welcome note

Dear colleagues,

Dear friends,

On behalf of the Montenegrin Association of Hematologists, it is my great honor and pleasure to welcome you to the 1st Congress of the Montenegrin Association of Hematologists with international participation (MAH 2024), which will be held in Budva from September 12th to 15th, 2024.

In addition to a large number of renowned experts in the field of hematology, the congress will also be attended by colleagues from diagnostics (pathophysiology, immunohistochemistry, molecular genetics, flow cytometry), who are of invaluable importance for an adequate approach to our patients. We are honored to have eminent experts from a wide range of countries, including the United Kingdom, Spain, Greece, Germany, Turkey, Albania, Romania, the Netherlands, Serbia, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and North Macedonia. The congress has been accredited as an international event by the Medical Chamber of Montenegro.

The topics are highly relevant and up-to-date, covering current developments in both the diagnosis and treatment of malignant hematological diseases and topics from benign hematology and hemostasis. Additionally, there will be discussions on hematopoietic stem cell transplantation and the contemporary treatment with CAR T-cells.

Lord Byron wrote about Montenegro: "At the moment of the planet's creation, the most beautiful encounter between land and sea must have been on the Montenegrin coast." We hope your encounter with Montenegro will be equally beautiful, creating an environment for advancing professional and friendly relationships.

Warm regards,

Dr. Enisa Zarić

President of Montenegrin Association of Hematologists

Congress President

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INFEKTIVNE KOMPLIKACIJE TOKOM PRVE INDUKCIONE TERAPIJE KOD BOLESNIKA SA AKUTNOM MIJELOIDNOM LEUKEMIJOM

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Uvod: Akutna mijeloidna leukemija (AML) je heterogenic hematološki malignitet koji se karakteriše klonskom ekspanzijom mijeloidnih blasta u kosnoj srži, perifernoj krvi i/ili drugim organima. Infektivne komplikacije su značajan uzrok morbiditeta i mortaliteta. Indukciona hemoterapije je povezana sa teškim infekcijama, dok je neutropenija često prisutan rizik.

Cilj rada: Istražiti prosečnu starost, polnu distribuciju, vrstu i učestalost infekcija, kao i ukupnu smrtnost od infekcija kod pacijenata sa AML tokom prve indukcione terapije. Utvrditi povezanost između starosti, pola, prisustva šećerne bolesti, broja leukocita, broja trombocita, vrednosti hemoglobina, procenta blasta u koštanoj srži, postignute remisije i ishoda sa pojavom infekcija.

Materijali i metode: Retrospektivno istraživanje sprovedeno u trogodišnjem periodu obuhvatilo je 36 pacijenata sa dijagnostikovanom AML koji su primili prvu indukcionu terapiju po protokolu „3+7“. Prikupljeni supodaci iz Kliničkog informativnog sistema Univerzitetskog kliničkog centra Vojvodine i analizirani statističkim metodama.

Rezultati: Infektivne komplikacije su se pojavile kod 86% pacijenata tokom prve indukcione terapije. Najčešće komplikacije su bile febrilna neutropenija (38.7%), pneumonija (14.5%) i plućna aspergiloza (14.5%). Statistički značajne razlike nisu nađene u starosti, polu, prisustvu šećerne bolesti, vrednostima hemoglobina, broju leukocita i trombocita, niti procentu blasta pre započinjanja terapije između pacijenata sa i bez infekcija. Ukupna smrtnost na kraju perioda praćenja iznosila je 3%.

Zaključak: Febrilna neutropenija je najčešća infektivna komplikacija tokom prve indukcione terapije kod pacijenata sa AML, a pneumonija i plućna aspergiloza su takođe značajno prisutne. Nije utvrđena značajna povezanost između analiziranih kliničkih i laboratorijskih parametara i pojave infekcija. Ukupna smrtnost je relativno niska, ali infektivne komplikacije ostaju ključan izazov u lečenju AML.

Ključne riječi: akutna mijeloidna leukemija; indukciona terapija; infekcije.

INFECTIOUS COMPLICATIONS DURING THE FIRST INDUCTION THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE MYELOID LEUKEMIA

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Introduction: Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a heterogeneous hematological malignancy characterized by the clonal expansion of myeloid blasts in the bone marrow, peripheral blood, and/or other organs. Infectious complications are a significant cause of morbidity and mortality. Induction chemotherapy is associated with severe infections, while neutropenia is often a present risk.

Aim of the study: To investigate the average age, gender distribution, type and frequency of infections, as well as the overall mortality from infections in AML patients during the first induction therapy. To determine the association between age, gender, presence of diabetes mellitus, leukocyte count, platelet count, hemoglobin levels, percentage of bone marrow blasts, achieved remission, and outcomes with the occurrence of infections.

Materials and methods: A retrospective study conducted over a three-year period included 36 patients diagnosed with AML who received the first induction therapy according to the "3+7" protocol. Data were collected from the Clinical Information System of the University Clinical Center of Vojvodina and analyzed using statistical methods.

Results: Infectious complications occurred in 86% of patients during the first induction therapy. The most common complications were febrile neutropenia (38.7%), pneumonia (14.5%), and pulmonary aspergillosis (14.5%). No statistically significant differences were found in age, gender, presence of diabetes mellitus, hemoglobin levels, leukocyte and platelet counts, or the percentage of blasts before the start of therapy between patients with and without infections. The overall mortality at the end of the follow-up period was 3%.

Conclusion: Febrile neutropenia is the most common infectious complication during the first induction therapy in AML patients, with pneumonia and pulmonary aspergillosis also being significantly present. No significant association was found between the analyzed clinical and laboratory parameters and the occurrence of infections. Overall mortality is relatively low, but infectious complications remain a key challenge in the treatment of AML.

Keywords: acute myeloid leukemia; induction therapy; infection